

Rawlings School of Divinity

The Isaiah 7:14 Controversy

An Interpretive Essay
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Isaiah
OBST 661

By

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Introduction

This essay will address the problem of the identity of Immanuel in Isaiah 7:14 by surveying the major views regarding the identity of the child. The historical background and the larger context of Isaiah 7 through 9 will be explored along with the meaning of almah and its use in Isaiah 7 and Matthew 1:23. Various articles, commentaries, and sources will be cited and documented to explain and defend the position regarding the identity. This essay will survey major views, critique and defend major viewpoints, and provide a conclusion of the issues treated in the problem surrounding the text.

Summary

In the Gospel of Matthew, the author cited Isaiah 7:14 as a basis of understanding the incarnation with the critical elements of the virgin birth bringing forth the God of the universe into the person of Jesus Christ who is God with us. The question of importance is whether the virgin birth of Jesus Christ was a fulfillment of prophecy with strict limits or a typological rendering. Barry Webb provides the historical background of Isaiah 7 through 9 along with the video lecture by Gary Yates.¹ Webb and Yates stated King Ahaz of Judah first refuses to join a coalition of nations to rout an Assyrian attack.² Isaiah then confronts Ahaz when he begins to fear the coalition of Ephraim made up of Israel and Syria.³ Ahaz rejects Isaiah's warning and assurance that God is with him and will protect Judah if he would make Jehovah their protector instead of Assyria, a wicked nation. Despite Isaiah's assurances and warnings, Ahaz chooses submission to Assyria over trusting God and continues with his plan. (2 Kings 16:7) Webb argues the unclear, enigmatic

¹Gary Yates, "Overview of Isaiah Video", Liberty University, iTunes U, http://learn.liberty.edu/webapps/portal/frameset.jsp?tab_tab_group_id=_2_1&url=/webapps/blackboard/excute/courseMain?course_id=_15956_1 (Accessed Jan, 16, 2014)

² Barry G. Webb, *The Message of Isaiah*. Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 1997. 61.

³ Paul D. Wegner, "How Many Virgins are in the Bible? (ISAIAH 7:14): A PROPHETIC PATTERN APPROACH". *Journal of the Evangelical Theological Society*, 54(3), 467-484. (2011) 468.

virgin sign is given because of Ahaz's refusal to accept a clear sign. (Is. 7:7-9) Webb believes 7:14 finds its ultimate fulfillment in Christ.⁴ James M. Hamilton argues for a typological fulfillment of the text in his article on the text. John Walton articulates the position almah cannot linguistically always mean virgin when it most often does not.⁵ Walton explores the meaning of Immanuel in the historical and biblical context. He believes the naming of the child is the sign of the beginning of the judgment of the two rulers who had aligned against Ahaz, an indication of the reality of God's presence.⁶ Walton demonstrates how hindsight is the means by which the appropriateness of a prophetic word is determined in the OT context. Under the inspiration of the Holy Spirit, Matthew when pondering the details of the virgin birth cannot help but notice how similar and appropriate are the words of 7:14 regardless of original context.⁷ C. R. North based upon exegesis throughout the Bible offers this translation, "The young woman is pregnant."⁸ Jewish scholars claimed Immanuel to be non-messianic and believed King Hezekiah to be the child. One of the more popular views is almah is one of Isaiah's wives and Immanuel is one of his sons.⁹

Critique

Webb's assessment of the sign of the virgin birth was given to Ahaz as a fulfillment of the command of God to Isaiah to speak to these people in ways they cannot understand. Webb states verse 13-16 is the key to understanding the sign.

Lest they see with their eyes, hear with their ears; understand with their hearts,

⁴ Webb, 62.

⁵ John H. Walton, "Isa 7:14 : What's in a Name?." *Journal Of The Evangelical Theological Society* 30, no. 3 (September 1, 1987): 289-306. *ATLA Religion Database with ATLA Serials, EBSCOhost* (accessed January 24, 2014): 293.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 295.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 300.

⁸ C.R. North, *The Interpreter's Dictionary of the Bible*, George A. Buttrick, ed. (Nashville:Parthenon Press, Eleventh Printing, 685-688, 1980): 686.

⁹ Herbert Martin Wolf, "Solution to the Immanuel prophecy in Isaiah 7:14-8:22." *Journal Of Biblical Literature* (1972) 91, no. 4: 449-456. *ATLA Religion Database with ATLASerials, EBSCOhost* (accessed January 26, 2014): 450.

Turn and be healed.

Webb wrongly sees this key as proof Ahaz was given a sign he could not understand.¹⁰ If the sign could be understood then what is the point in giving the sign? Walton's view is a more comprehensive exegesis providing the basis of the sign as the proclamation that a woman known to Ahaz, perhaps one of his own wives is pregnant and will give birth to a son who she will name God-with-Us because the protection of God has already begun as Judah was delivered from the threat of destruction by Ephraim's monarchs. The entire discussion of the text from 7:1-25 speaks of deliverance from this threat. Walton wrote,

The bottom line of the statement of the sign is that this son will be named Immanuel, "God with us." I am suggesting, therefore, that all evidence points to the naming of the child as the sign.¹¹

Since the naming of the child is the sign, not the nature of the birth, it can be said the coming of the child is followed by the reunion of Judah and Israel (7:17, Micah 5:3b). The content of the prophecy speaks in the historic context to have the child's life be the indication of when certain aspects of the oracle are fulfilled. Before the child is old enough to choose between good and evil, still an infant, Syria and Ephraim will be devastated. By 732 BC Damascus is destroyed and the child is only one and half to two years old.¹² However, a greater understanding of prophecy and its role as typological can be seen in Matthew, Acts, and Revelation. Immanuel is fulfilled in Christ as the Christian biblical writers appreciate it.¹³ Since this student believes in the inerrancy of Scripture, the Holy Spirit did not make an error by pointing to Isaiah 7:14 as a proclamation of the reality of the birth of Christ to a virgin being by the Holy Spirit.

¹⁰ Webb, 62.

¹¹ Walton, 295.

¹² North, 687.

¹³ Walton, 296.

Immanuel is latched onto by Matthew to explain and proclaim the great events he had witnessed. (Matt.1:23) Matthew has no problem using other images in the OT and calling it fulfilled prophecy. He cites Hosea 11:1 saying it is fulfilled prophecy when Jesus is taken to Egypt to flee the wrath of Herod and yet the context in Hosea is referring to the calling of Israel out of slavery in Egypt. (Matt. 2:15) North offers a solution to the problem posed by Matthew's use of 7:14 is the problem of contemporary critical theologians¹⁴ and Jewish theologians who take offense to the use of prophecy in this manner.¹⁵ Isaiah and Hosea did not know they were writing about Jesus when they penned their words but the Holy Spirit helps Christians see all of Scripture as fulfilled in Christ in one way or another. The question lies in how Scripture and prophecy are viewed. Isaiah prophesied to his contemporaries of impending events however Isaiah can be viewed as inspiration and becomes inspiration to NT authors. Just because mythological yearning of cultures depicts a deity who dies and rises again does not mean the death and resurrection of Christ is mythological but rather the historicization of deep longing however crudely depicted in ancient minds and writings are realized. The Immanuel of Isaiah 7, 9, and 11 is the intermediary of ancient longing for a God to be with mankind and the fulfillment found in Christ.¹⁶ When Matthew uses the word fulfillment, he writes in the broadest and fullest sense.

Conclusion

For eighteen hundred years the traditional view of Isaiah 7:14 was unchallenged by Catholic and Protestant scholars. It is now evident from Matthew 2:15 how prophetic literature is

¹⁴ Ibid., 297.

¹⁵ North, 687.

¹⁶ Ibid., 688.

liberally used to illustrate a fuller meaning of the text as opposed to a literal fulfillment.¹⁷ Both the Isaiah and Hosea passages have little to do with messianic prophecies within their contextual construct. These OT passages had little intention of predicting a future event that included the coming of Jesus Christ as Messiah and yet Matthew freely used both passages to illustrate the nature and events surrounding the virgin birth, the incarnation, and the flight to Egypt.¹⁸ The virginity of Mary is not dependent on the text of 7:14 because Matthew explicitly states her miraculous conception by the Holy Spirit.¹⁹ Matthew is not the only NT writer to use fulfillment language to demonstrate typological fulfillment and this understanding will greatly serve Bible students to interpret Luke 4:17-19 as Jesus recites Isaiah 61.²⁰ This essay has surveyed major views, critiqued and defended major viewpoints, and provided a conclusion of the issues treated in the problem surrounding Isaiah 7:14.

¹⁷ Ibid, 687.

¹⁸ James M. Hamilton Jr., “The Virgin will conceive: Typology in Isaiah and Fulfillment in Matthew, The Use of Isaiah 7:14 in Matthew 1:18–23”, *Tyndale Fellowship Biblical Theology Study Group*, (July 6–8, 2005) (accessed January 24, 2014): 24.

¹⁹ Wolf, 455.

²⁰ Hamilton, 23.

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